

Modelling of Heat-Driven Water Treatment Systems: Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) model in Modelica

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Abstract

The improvement of water and energy use in the industrial sector is an important concern for decarbonisation of industries, as well as to improve the overall techno-economic performance of single plants. The improvement of water efficiency, in particular, is a potential approach in the context of its interdependencies to energy use, comprehended by the *water-energy nexus*. A practical application corresponds to the use of heat-driven water treatment units such as multi-effect distillation (MED). Such technology is commonly used for the desalination of seawater, as well as industrial waste saline water streams. This work presents a customised model for an industrial MED unit, namely its assembling using the object-oriented Modelica language, and also a brief economic assessment for the viability of such unit for industrial application. The model was validated with literature data by comparing the theoretical temperature profiles with the simulation results. A payback time of 7.1 years was estimated by excluding negligible parcels of operating expenses (OPEX) for the MED project, which may be considered reasonable in terms of economic feasibility.

Keywords: water and energy integration; Multi-effect distillation; waste heat recovery; water efficiency; Modelica.

1. Introduction

Water and energy integration involve a set of methods, measures and practices to improve their usage in industry (Alnouri et al., 2014), corresponding to two of the most extensively used resources in an industrial plant. The interdependencies of water and energy resources, namely the understanding of the improvement of water use through the understanding of the use of energy, are studied in the scope of the *water-energy nexus* (Oliveira et al., 2019). Moreover, practices of *Combined Water and Energy Integration* corresponds to the simultaneous application of water recirculation and heat recovery principles. In practice, these may be implemented through the use of a water stream as a waste heat stream (Savulescu and Alva-Argaez, 2013). An alternative approach which makes use of the principle of heat recovery, relies on the waste heat potential from a waste stream to set the operation of a water treatment and recirculation system.

In the alignment of the latter approach, this work studies a Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) technology, which may be used (among other applications) for industrial wastewater treatment, namely to desalinate saline water streams (Rahimi and Chua,

2017). This technology makes part of a set of heat-driven water treatment technologies, with the operation of such system needing the supply of a sensible heat source. The approach considered in this work, explores the MED technology, namely the development and validation of a numerical model using the Modelica language, followed by the analysis of its performance and a brief economic assessment in an industrial plant.

2. Modelling of a Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) Unit

The modelling and simulation procedure have been performed using the Modelica object-oriented modelling language, namely using the open-source software OpenModelica 1.18.1. The models for each one of the operational units as well as the whole model have been developed through the use and adaptation of the existing code presented in the ThermoPower Modelica Library (Politecnico di Milano, 2021).

2.1. Theoretical Model

The study performed by Rahimi and Chua (Rahimi and Chua, 2017) presents an overall model that describes the physical phenomena occurring in a MED unit. Following this work, a conventional MED configuration model is presented. The assembling of the MED model considered 3 main components: i) first effect, ii) second-to-last effects and iii) condenser sections. The physical phenomena model described by Rahimi and Chua (2017) is based on mass and energy balances, including an analysis of the heat transfer and fluid phenomena. The model enables a division of the temperature profiles of the effects by zones, which divide specific different sections with different trends for the respective temperature profiles of the hot and cold streams. The mass and energy balance equations for each section are presented in Table 1, while the temperature profiles for each section are represented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Temperature profiles for a) first effect section, b) second-to-last effects section without flashed feed stream, c) second to last effect section with flashed feed stream and d) condenser section (adapted from (Rahimi and Chua, 2017))

Table 1. Mass and Energy balances for a conventional MED system

Balance	Zone	Equation
Mass Balance	First effect	$M_{F,1} = M_{B,1} + M_{V,1}$ (1)
	Second-to-last effects	$M_{F,1} \cdot X_{F,1} = M_{B,1} \cdot X_{B,1}$ (2)
		$M_{F,k} = M_{B,k} + M_{V,k}$ (3)
	Condenser	$M_{HS,k} = M_{V,k-1}$ (4)
		$M_{F,k} \cdot X_{F,k} = M_{B,k} \cdot X_{B,k}$ (5)
$M_{HS,cond} = M_{V,n}$ (6)		
Enthalpy Balance	First effect	$M_{F,1} \cdot h_{F,1} + M_{HS,1} \cdot h_{HS,1,in} = M_{B,1} \cdot h_{B,1} + M_{V,1} \cdot h_{V,1} + M_{HS,1} \cdot h_{HS,1,out}$ (7)
	Second-to-last effects	$M_{F,k} \cdot h_{F,k} + M_{HS,k} \cdot h_{HS,k,in} = M_{B,k} \cdot h_{B,k} + M_{V,k} \cdot h_{V,k} + M_{HS,k} \cdot h_{HS,k,out}$ (8)
		$h_{HS,k,out} = h_{f,sat}(P_k)$ (9)
	Condenser	$M_{HS,cond} \cdot h_{HS,cond,in} + M_C \cdot h_{C,in} = M_{HS,cond} \cdot h_{HS,cond,out} + M_C \cdot h_{C,out}$ (10)
		$h_{HS,cond,in} = h_{v,nn}$ (11)
		$h_{HS,cond,out} = h_{f,sat}(P_n)$ (12)

2.2. Development of a MED Unit model in Modelica

The procedure of this work involved the development of a model for each component of a MED unit: i) First effect, ii) Second-to-last effects and iii) Condenser. Each one of these models was assembled considering the mass and energy balances and the heat transfer along the effects and condenser. In order to build the computational models, it was necessary to adapt such equations, in order to simplify and enable the convergence of the simulation. For instance, the heat transfer equations were discretized using the finite volume method (FVM). The assembled model (considering a total of four MED effects) is represented in Fig. 2 (in which Effects 3 and 4 are omitted). The equations used to describe the heat transfer phenomena in a MED unit are presented in Table 2 and Table 3. It is to note that, in the sets of equations, i designates a node of the control volume of an effect or the condenser.

Fig. 2. Assembling of the MED unit model in OpenModelica

Table 2. Model equations for heat transfer associated to Effect 1 and its zones

Section	Zone	Heat Transfer Equations
Effect 1	Zone 1	$q(i) = M_{HS,1} \cdot C_{p,HS,1} \cdot (T_{HS,1}(i) - T_{HS,1}(i+1))$ (13)
		$q(i) = M_{F,1} \cdot C_{p,w} \cdot (T_{F,1}(i+1) - T_{F,1}(i))$ (14)
		$dT(i) = ((T_{HS,1}(i) - T_{F,1}(i)) + (T_{HS,1}(i+1) - T_{F,1}(i+1))) \cdot 0.5$ (15)
	Zone 2	$q(i) = U_{1,1} \cdot (A(i+1) - A(i)) \cdot dT(i)$ (16)
		$q(i) = M_{HS,1} \cdot C_{p,HS,1} \cdot (T_{HS,1}(i) - T_{HS,1}(i+1))$ (17)
	$dT(i) = ((T_{HS,1}(i) - T_{F,1,sat}) + (T_{HS,1}(i+1) - T_{F,1,sat})) \cdot 0.5$ (18)	
	$q(i) = U_{1,2} \cdot (A(i+1) - A(i)) \cdot dT$ (19)	

Table 3. Model equations for heat transfer associated to Effect k, Condenser and its respective zones

Section	Zone	Heat Transfer Equations	Section
Effect k	Zone 2	$q(i) = M_{HS,k} \cdot (h_{HS,k}(i) - h_{HS,k}(i+1))$	(20)
		$q(i) = M_{F,k} \cdot C_{P_w} \cdot (T_{F,k}(i) - T_{F,k}(i+1))$	(21)
		$dT(i) = \left((T_{HS,k,sat} - T_{F,k}(i)) + (T_{HS,k,sat} - T_{F,k}(i+1)) \right) \cdot 0.5$	(22)
	Zone 3	$q(i) = U_{k,z} \cdot (A(i+1) - A(i)) \cdot dT(i)$	(23)
		$q(i) = M_{HS,k} \cdot (h_{HS,k}(i) - h_{HS,k}(i+1))$	(24)
		$dT(i) = \left((T_{HS,k,sat} - T_{F,k,sat}) + (T_{HS,k,sat} - T_{F,k,sat}) \right) \cdot 0.5$	(25)
Condenser	Zone 2	$q(i) = U_{k,z} \cdot (A(i+1) - A(i)) \cdot dT(i)$	(26)
		$q = M_{F,cond} \cdot C_{P_w} \cdot (T_{F,cond}(i) - T_{F,cond}(i+1))$	(27)
		$dT(i) = \left((T_{HS,n,sat} - T_{F,cond}(i)) + (T_{HS,k,sat} - T_{F,cond}(i+1)) \right) \cdot 0.5$	(28)
		$q(i) = U_{cond,z} \cdot (A(i+1) - A(i)) \cdot dT(i)$	(29)

The following modelling assumptions have been considered: steady-state simulation; constant and equal recovery ratio of the primary MED effects; negligible heat losses and pressure losses; constant temperature and salinity of the inlet feed water stream; null salinity of the outlet treated water stream; a temperature difference of 2.5 °C between the condensed vapour and the outlet concentrate streams for primary MED effects. The heat source stream, which is the hot stream in Effect 1, is a liquid with a specific heat capacity of 6643 J/(°C.kg), entering in Effect 1 at a temperature of 170.0 °C and at pressure of 1.5 bar.

2.3. Simulation Results and Model Validation

The model validation has been performed in order to assess its reliability and accuracy in comparison with the theoretical data (Rahimi and Chua, 2017). In this work, model validation has been performed by comparing the heat transfer phenomena occurring in each one of the sections, namely the temperature profiles. The temperature profiles achieved by the simulation of the model for each one of the components of the MED unit are represented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Obtained temperature profiles for a) Effect 1, b) Effect 2, c) Effect 3, d) Effect 4, e) Condenser

By comparing the theoretical temperature profiles reported in the literature with the simulated ones (respectively Fig. 1 and 3), it is observed that the simulated temperature profiles are overall consistent with the theoretical ones. The temperature profile of the cold fluid for the zone 2 of effects 2, 3 and 4 (second-to-last effects) presents a sharper variation compared to the linear variation shown in Fig. 1(c), which may be attributed to the use of FVM method for the computation of mean temperature difference, which produces relatively more accurate results. Considering these aspects, it is possible to conclude that the developed model is overall consistent on the prospect of the performed simulation being able to reproduce the real phenomena.

3. Economic Assessment

In addition to the development of a model for a MED unit, Rahimi and Chua (2017) expanded their analysis to a generalized method for the economic assessment of such desalination installations. The simplistic economic model included the capital cost and payback period associated to a MED project, as detailed in Table 4, while the economic savings and payback period estimations considering the water savings results obtained by the simulation are presented in Table 5. A water price of 1.1952 €/m³ was considered for the conversion of water production (assumed to be equal to potential freshwater savings) related to the economic savings.

Table 4. Capital costs and associated payback period determination for a MED unit (Rahimi and Chua, 2017)

Capital Cost	$TCC_{MED} = 2535 \cdot D_c^{0.9751}$	(30)
Payback Period	$PB = TCC_{MED} / (Sav - AEC)$	(31)

Table 5. Determination of water production, economic savings and payback period

Water Production (D_c) (m³/day)	843.28
Water Production (D_c) (dam³/year)	292.41
Investment costs (TCC_{MED}) (k€)	1807.57
Electricity costs (AEC) (k€/year)	95.21
Economic savings (Sav) (k€/year)	349.49
Payback Period (PB) (years)	7.1

Considering the parameters listed in Table 5 and applying equations (30) and (31), a payback period of about 7.1 is obtained. Note that this analysis has not considered certain parcels of the OPEX, for instance, costs associated to chemicals (which includes the costs associated to the acquisition and use of the heat source stream), maintenance, spares, incomes and labour. These are assumed to be common to both MED and conventional wastewater treatment. In this case, these parcels are considered to have already been taken into account in the project of the industrial site in which the MED unit is installed. The payback lies within the acceptable economic viability interval 4 – 16 years of payback time (Baniasad Askari and Ameri, 2021), and therefore it is possible to say that this project is economically feasible. However, considering different studies for the techno-economic assessment of thermal vapour compression MED units, in which payback times correspond to less than 5 years, it is concluded that the MED unit project considered in this work still requires further analysis in terms of potential improvements.

4. Conclusions

This work presents the study of a heat-driven water treatment system, in particular through the exploitation of the multi-effect distillation (MED) technology. This has been achieved by the development and assembling of numerical models describing a conventional MED unit, using the Modelica language. Literature data has been

considered as case-study enabling the modelling of MED unit. The modelling results were validated by comparing the temperature profiles with the theoretical ones. The simulated temperature profiles were, in general, consistent with the theoretical ones, thus ensuring the validity of the model for the simulation of the real occurring phenomena. Furthermore, a brief economic assessment was performed to assess the viability of the MED plant project in an industrial plant. A payback period of 7.1 years was determined, suggesting that the desalination project may be considered economically viable (considering a reasonable payback time of 4 – 16 years), although this is still high when compared to payback periods of other MED unit projects. Further improvement measures (for instance, improved configurations of multi-effect distillation such as preheated MED, boosted MED and flash boosted MED units) will be analysed in the following studies.

Nomenclature

<i>A</i>	Heat Transfer Area (m ²)	Subscripts	
<i>AEC</i>	Cost of electricity (€/year)	<i>B</i>	Concentrate/ Brine Stream
<i>D_t</i>	Daily quantity of water production (m ³ /day)	<i>C</i>	Cooling Water Stream
<i>h</i>	Specific Enthalpy (J/kg)	<i>Cold</i>	Cold Stream
<i>M</i>	Mass flow rate (kg/s)	<i>cond</i>	Condenser
<i>P</i>	Pressure (Pa)	<i>F</i>	Feed Water Stream
<i>PB</i>	Payback Period (years)	<i>Hot</i>	Hot stream
<i>TCC</i>	Capital Cost (€)	<i>HS</i>	Heat Source Stream
<i>Sav</i>	Economic Savings (€/year)	<i>in</i>	Inlet
<i>U</i>	Overall Heat Transfer Coefficient (W/(m ² .°C))	<i>k</i>	Effect number designation
<i>X</i>	Salt concentration (ppm)	<i>MED</i>	MED unit
		<i>n</i>	Total number of effects in a MED unit
		<i>out</i>	Outlet
		<i>total</i>	Total
		<i>sat</i>	Saturation
		<i>V</i>	Vapour Stream

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